

THE SECRET LIVES OF GREAT ENGLISH AND AMERICAN WRITERS

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Abstract: Getting acquainted with the biography of famous writers, whose eventful lives are reflected in their exciting works, is always interesting for the readers. This article collects quite a few unexpected, random, but really interesting facts about some of our favorite English and American writers, including their lives, habits and interests.

Kew words: interesting facts, American literature, behaviour, bestselling works, habits.

- Charles John Dickens has superstitious behaviour. The most famous oddity of Charles is that the writer could not sit at the table or go to bed with his head not to the north. Charles Dickens believed that sleeping facing north would improve his writing skills, so he always slept with his head to the north. He also sat facing north when he wrote his great works. Charles wrote his brilliant works in this direction. Legends say that Dickens was addicted to hypnosis and mesmerism (telepathic communication between people and animals), and even voluntarily fell into a trance. One of Dickens's favorite pastimes was going to the Paris mortuary, where unidentified bodies were exhibited.

- Agatha Christie worked in a military hospital too. She was a nurse during the First World War. Later she worked in a pharmacy. She was knowledgeable in poisons, so that many murders, written her books were performed with the help of knowing poisons.

In addition, she suffered from dysgraphia, that is, she could hardly write by hand herself. So all her popular novels were dictated. Agatha Christie said that a warm bath was a place where she came up with the plots for her famous murder mysteries and she really liked to think out her novels while eating fresh apples. As of today, Christie remains the bestselling murder mystery novelist of all time, so without any doubt we can say that her method obviously worked.

- George Eliot was actually a woman. During her period of life women authors were not as highly regarded as men, so Mary Ann Evans wrote her books under this pseudonym. As a writer George Eliot, Mary Evans was able to write various novels considered as the best stories of all time.

Mary was a completely unattractive, ugly woman. She was short and skinny. I.S.Turgenev knew her personally and he said that he had never met a more ugly woman in his life than the writer Mary. But also, Turgenev who was considered as a well-known connoisseur and admirer of female beauty, said about George Eliot: "I know that she is bad-looking, but when I am with her, I do not see it." Turgenev admitted that it was George Eliot who first made him realize that person can fall madly in love with a completely ugly woman.

- Romantic legend Lord Byron was very fond of animals. When he studied at Cambridge, he was forbidden to have dogs in the rooms and then he decided to get a bear cub. Since bears were not mentioned in the ban, the university could not do anything about him and his animals. He always traveled with his dozens of animals. Just a few of the pets that made it from Byron's English estate to Venice include ten horses, three monkeys, three peacocks, eight dogs, five cats, one crane, one falcon, one eagle, and one crow. During his life, Byron had such pets like a fox, a badger, a crocodile, an eagle, a crane and a heron.

Byron was very fond of swimming too. He could easily swim 5 miles (9 km). At the age of 21, Byron made a bet that he would swim across the Tahoe River, although there were the fast current and several miles wide. In 1809 he swam across the mouth of the Tahoe River. In 1810 he was able to swim across the Dardanelles in an hour and ten minutes. When there was a competition in Venice in 1818, Byron won the victory by holding out on the water for 4 hours and 20 minutes and covering a distance of several miles, so that the Italians called him "the Englishman-fish".

- Emily Dickinson was one of the most reclusive poets in American literary history. She was an unordinary girl, who always wore white dresses at any time of the year and she never signed her letters. From the 1850s till her death, Dickinson mainly stayed within her Amherst family home and only went outside to tend to the garden. She did not even leave her upstairs bedroom to attend her father's funeral downstairs. Researchers now believe that Dickinson suffered from rheumatic fever, a painful inflammation of the iris that caused her to avoid all light.

REFERENCES:

1. Schlottman A. 150 Interesting Facts About Our Favorite Authors / A. Schlottman. — 2016. <https://booksonthewall.com/blog/10-interesting-facts-10-famous-authors/>

2. Cadman B. Interesting Facts About Writers And Writing / B.Cadman. — 2019. <https://writerslife.org/interesting-facts-writers-writing/>

3. Викторова О. Английские писатели. Такими вы их не знаете! /

О. Викторовна. — 2019. <https://blog.tutoronline.ru/anglijskie-pisateli-takimi-vy-ih-ne-znaete>

4. Tatiana. Английские писатели и их истории / Tatiana. —2021. <https://englishstory.ru/english-writers.html>

5. Шнакенберг Р. Тайная жизнь великих писателей / Р. Шнакенберг. — Livelib. — 2010. ISBN: 978-5-98697-206-0. <https://www.livelib.ru/book/1000456478-tajnaya-zhizn-velikih-pisatelej-robert-shnakenberg>